

Mapping of Organizational Culture, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment in the Star-Rated Hotel Industry in Semarang City

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ABSTRACT

The star-rated hotel industry in Semarang City is facing increasingly fierce competition, along with the growth of the tourism and MICE sectors, which demand improved service quality based on employee performance. This study aims to describe the conditions of organizational culture, work engagement, organizational commitment, and employee performance in star-rated hotels in Semarang City. The research approach uses a quantitative method with an explanatory survey design. The study population consisted of all 6,064 permanent employees of star-rated hotels in Semarang City, with a sample of 230 respondents selected using the Slovin formula. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results indicate that organizational culture, work engagement, and organizational commitment fall into the good category, with an average value for each exceeding 4.00. Employee performance also shows a positive perception, although there are still several aspects that need to be improved, particularly related to the effectiveness of work completion, work innovation, and understanding of SOPs. These findings confirm that strengthening internal organizational factors is a crucial prerequisite for enhancing employee performance and the competitiveness of star-rated hotels in Semarang City.

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KEYWORDS: organizational culture, work engagement, organizational commitment, employee performance, star hotels.

1. INTRODUCTION

Semarang, the economic center of Central Java, boasting a variety of attractive tourist attractions, continues to evolve into a leading tourism destination and MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conventions, and Exhibitions) city. This requires adequate accommodations that can provide the best comfort and experience for tourists and event participants. Over the past decade, the number of star-rated hotels has increased significantly, in line with the growth of tourism, trade, and MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions) activities. Data from the Central Java Provincial Statistics Agency (2025) indicates that more than 100 star-rated hotels are actively operating in Semarang. However, this increase in the number of hotels is not always accompanied by an increase in service quality and guest satisfaction, as evidenced by numerous negative guest reviews on digital platforms such as TripAdvisor and Google Reviews, which highlight inconsistent, slow/unresponsive, and unprofessional service from hotel staff. Furthermore, the increasing number of hotels also triggers increasingly fierce competition.

Increasingly fierce competition between hotels not only impacts pricing and promotions but also triggers various internal challenges related to human resource management, such as high employee turnover, interdepartmental conflict, low work engagement, and customer complaints about the quality of hotel staff service. This decline in service quality directly impacts the hotel's digital reputation and decreases guest trust. This condition encourages every hotel management to strive to increase competitiveness through various strategies, both in terms of marketing, service, and the quality of human resources. One important aspect that is the focus of attention is improving employee performance, considering that the quality of service provided is highly dependent on individual and team performance in carrying out their duties. To achieve high employee performance in the hotel industry, hotel employees are required to possess a combination of various aspects, including strong physical and mental abilities, adequate knowledge and skills, good interpersonal skills, adherence to high standards, as well as flexibility and the ability to adapt to changing times.

“Mapping of Organizational Culture, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment in the Star-Rated Hotel Industry in Semarang City”

Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the hospitality sector is recovering; however, work pressures are actually increasing due to HR efficiency and demands for excellent service, which impact employee stress levels and job satisfaction. In service industries, such as hotels, employee performance is a key factor in determining a hotel's operational success and competitive advantage. It is also a crucial component in determining service quality, hotel image, and customer loyalty. Therefore, strategic efforts are necessary to maintain and enhance employee performance in the face of increasing service demands. As a service industry that relies heavily on direct interaction between employees and guests, the quality of service provided is primarily determined by the individual and collective performance of employees (Chiang & Hsieh, 2012). In star-rated hotels, demands for professionalism, speed of service, and interpersonal skills are particularly high, given the premium expectations of the guest segment served. Employee performance will be maximized when the organization effectively manages its employees. As an organizational asset, employees' skills, abilities, emotions, desires, demands, needs, and limitations must be well-managed so that they can develop and feel cared for. Failure to do so can lead to a decline in employee performance.

Employee performance not only reflects work productivity but is also a crucial indicator in building a positive image and fostering customer loyalty. In the service-driven hospitality industry, guest satisfaction is heavily influenced by direct interactions with hotel staff. Therefore, to survive and thrive amidst increasingly fierce competition, hotels must address internal factors that contribute to employee performance, such as organizational culture, work engagement, and organizational commitment.

One of the main variables influencing employee performance is employee job satisfaction (Susanto, 2019). According to Dole et al. (2001), job satisfaction is defined as a person's reactions and feelings toward their workplace. Employee job satisfaction is a personalized measure of an individual's feelings toward their job (Robbins, 2012).

Literature Review. The purpose of this study is to describe organizational culture, work engagement, organizational commitment, and employee performance at star-rated hotels in Semarang City.

Practically, the results of this research are expected to provide benefits for: Star hotel management in Semarang City, as a strategic consideration in managing human resources, especially in designing policies that can increase employee job satisfaction and performance. Hotel Human Resources Department, in formulating more targeted work programs based on internal factors such as organizational culture, work involvement, and level of employee commitment to the organization. Stakeholder hospitality industry, including hotel associations (Indonesian Hotel and

Restaurant Association), HR consultants, and regional policy makers, to understand the importance of organizational factors in building service-based competitive advantage. Further research, as a reference and basis for conducting further studies with a similar model approach, both in different geographical contexts and industrial sectors.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Employee performance is a crucial factor in organizational success, as it reflects the extent to which an employee fulfills tasks and responsibilities according to established standards. Luthans et al. (2021) view performance as a set of behaviors that are relevant to achieving organizational goals, which includes both in-role performance and extra-role performance, such as cooperation and initiative.

Gomes (2008) defines employee performance as an expression of output, efficiency, and effectiveness that are closely related to productivity. In line with this, Robbins & Judge (2019) view performance as the result of an individual's work in carrying out their assigned tasks, with reference to effectiveness, efficiency, compliance with regulations, and contribution to team and organizational goals. This emphasis on effectiveness and efficiency is highly relevant to the dynamic and customer-satisfaction-oriented characteristics of the hospitality industry.

Mathis & Jackson (2019). He added that performance is what employees do or do not do in their work, meaning it is not only assessed based on the final result, but also on their work attitudes and behavior. Similarly, Mangkunegara (2017) emphasizes quantitative (number of outputs) and qualitative (accuracy, precision, and customer satisfaction) aspects in assessing performance. Fernandez & de Bustillo (2023) also highlight the combination of quantitative and qualitative aspects as complementary elements to produce optimal contributions to the organization.

Organizational culture refers to how employees perceive the cultural characteristics of an organization. Different organizations have distinct cultures, and therefore, they employ different approaches to applying cultural meaning. According to Robbins & Judge (2019) Organizational culture is a system of shared meanings regarding primary values that are shared and valued by the organization, which functions to create a clear distinction between one organization and another, create a sense of identity for the members of the organization, facilitate the emergence of collective commitment to the organization, increase the stability of the social system, and create a mechanism for making meaning and control that guides the formation of attitudes and behavior of the members of the organization.

“Mapping of Organizational Culture, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment in the Star-Rated Hotel Industry in Semarang City”

Furthermore, Luthans et al. (2021) stated that "organizational culture is the norms and values that guide the behavior of organizational members. Each member will behave in accordance with the prevailing culture to be accepted by their environment." This is emphasized by Armstrong (2020), who states that organizational culture is a set of values, beliefs, or norms that have long been shared by members of the organization (employees) as a guideline for behavior and solving organizational problems. As Schein & Schein (2017) describe, organizational culture is a model of basic assumptions discovered or developed by a group of people as employees learn to solve problems, adapt to the external environment, and integrate into the internal environment.

Edison et al. (2016) state that organizational culture is the result of a process of unification and integration of previously instilled cultural styles and/or attitudes into new norms and philosophies that foster group energy and pride in achieving specific goals. Cultural stability depends on utility values that shape and influence the way people work.

Based on the description above, although the concept of organizational culture elicits diverse perspectives, there is agreement among cultural experts on how to define it. Essentially, organizational culture relates to a system of shared meaning held by members.

Organizational culture reflects the common perceptions of its members. Therefore, organizations expect people from disparate backgrounds to adapt to the culture in which they work, utilizing different cultural characteristics. Robbins & Judge (2019) state that 7 primary characteristics together capture the essence of organizational culture.

Job involvement is the extent to which an individual is psychologically involved in his or her work and considers job performance to be important to his or her self-concept. Luthans et al. (2021) state that job engagement reflects an employee's level of identification with their job and their willingness to devote their full energy and attention to their tasks. Employees with high engagement will demonstrate loyalty to their tasks and take full responsibility for the results of their work.

Meanwhile, work engagement, according to Robbins & Judge (2019), is the degree to which employees feel passionate, involved, and emotionally attached to their work. Employees with high job engagement consistently give their best effort to their work, often exceeding the job's requirements.

Employee job engagement is a constructive approach that touches on nearly every aspect of human resource management known to date. Another view defines job involvement as the extent to which an individual is psychologically invested in their work, considering their performance a measure of their self-worth. Because work is seen as important and meaningful to individuals, they devote

deep attention and thought to it, thus making them engaged with their work.

Organizational commitment is a psychological state that describes an individual's emotional, rational, and moral attachment to their organization. Allen & Meyer (1996) define organizational commitment as a psychological state that binds an individual to their organization and has implications for the decision to continue membership in that organization.

This definition is reinforced by another view, which states that organizational commitment reflects the extent to which employees believe in and accept the organization's goals and have a desire to remain part of it. (Mathis & Jackson, 2019) This view underscores the importance of employee loyalty and active engagement in realizing the organization's vision and mission.

Additionally, commitment is also considered an attitude that reflects loyalty and a sustained concern for the organization's sustainability. (Luthans et al., 2021) This reflects employee involvement in efforts to achieve shared goals and the process of internalizing organizational values.

In another part, Saks (2019) defines job engagement as a positive, enthusiastic, and performance-oriented psychological state that arises from a mutually beneficial relationship between an individual and an organization. This engagement encourages employees to actively participate in achieving goals.

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

This research is a quantitative explanatory research. Explanatory research aims to elucidate the causal relationships between variables by testing formulated hypotheses. The method used in this study is a survey, a technique for collecting primary data from respondents through the distribution of structured questionnaires. Surveys were chosen because they can reach a large number of respondents and allow for generalization of results to a broader population. (Singarimbun & Effendi, 2011).

3.2 Population and Sample

The population in this study comprises all permanent employees of star-classified hotels 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 in Semarang City, totaling 6,064 people (see Table 2). These employees are spread across 109 star-classified hotels in Semarang City (see Table 3).

The following table presents the number of permanent employees of star-rated hotels in Semarang City, categorized by star classification and gender, as of 2025. The table presents the number of hotels, rooms, and beds available in star hotels, categorized by star classification, in Semarang City in 2020.

“Mapping of Organizational Culture, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment in the Star-Rated Hotel Industry in Semarang City”

Based on calculations using the Slovin formula with a population of 6,064 people and a margin of error of 6.5%, the sample size was 227.9, rounded up to 228 respondents. However, because the Slovin calculation only provides an estimate of the minimum sample size needed to represent the population, the researcher decided to increase the sample size to 230 respondents. Thus, the sample size used in this study was set at 230 respondents.

3.3 Descriptive Analysis Techniques

Descriptive respondent analysis is used to obtain a description of the respondents, as measured by several indicators asked in the questionnaire. The analysis technique used is descriptive statistics, resulting in an average (mean) value for each indicator asked.

Table 1. Description of Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	106	46.1
	Woman	124	53.9
Age	20 - 30 years	54	23.5
	31 – 40 years old	73	31.7
	41 – 50 years old	98	42.6
	More than 50 years	5	2.2
Education	Diploma Graduate	57	24.8
	Graduated with a Bachelor's degree	87	37.8
	Graduated from Masters	1	0.4
	Graduated from high school	85	37.0

Source: Primary data, processed (2025)

The analysis of respondent characteristics reveals that the majority of respondents in this study were female, comprising 53.9% (124 people), while male respondents accounted for 46.1% (106 people). This distribution suggests that female involvement in research related to employee satisfaction and performance is quite prominent, offering different perspectives on perceptions of organizational culture, work engagement, and job satisfaction.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

4.1.1 Respondent Characteristics

Respondent characteristics indicate a general description of the respondents used as a research sample representing permanent hotel employees in Semarang. Respondent characteristics in this study were based on gender, age, and the highest level of education.

This study involved 230 respondents, all of whom were employees of a star hotel in Semarang City. Based on the results of data collection in this study, the following describes the characteristics of respondents in terms of gender, age, and education.

Figure 2. Gender

In terms of age, respondents were dominated by the 41–50 age group at 42.6%, followed by the 31–40 age group at 31.7%, then the 20–30 age group at 23.5%, and the remaining 2.2% were over 50 years old. This data indicates that the majority of respondents are in their productive and mature working years, so they

are expected to provide relevant and accurate information related to the variables in the study.

Education

Figure 3. Education

Meanwhile, based on educational level, the majority of respondents (37.8%) held a Bachelor's degree (S1), followed by high school graduates (37.0%), diploma graduates (24.8%), and a small percentage (0.4%) had a Master's degree (S2). This indicates that the majority of respondents have a secondary education level or higher, which is crucial for understanding organizational policies and work processes at their respective companies.

Age

Figure 4. Age

4.1.2 Descriptive Research Results

A descriptive analysis of the research variables in this study was conducted to provide an overview of the variables according to respondents' perceptions. Because this study employed a 1-5 Likert scale, respondents' perceptions of their answers were determined by examining the mean score for each question item. Umar (2014) categorizes the mean score of respondents' answers on a Likert scale of 1-5 with the following criteria: a mean value between 1.00 and 2.33 indicates a tendency towards low

perception in respondents; while a mean value between 2.33 and 3.67 indicates moderate perception, and a mean value between 3.67 and 5.00 indicates a tendency towards high perception.

4.1.3 Description Organizational culture

The results of the descriptive analysis on the organizational culture variable indicate that the lowest mean is found in three indicators, namely X1.3, X1.5, and X1.11, each with a mean value of 4.10. This value indicates that the aspects of decentralization of decision-making, employee initiative, and sense of job security are still perceived relatively lower than other indicators in the same variable. Overall, the organizational culture variable has been assessed well by respondents, with an overall average of 4.18; however, there is still room for improvement in these aspects. Improvement in these three aspects can strengthen the overall organizational culture in the star-rated hotel environment in Semarang City.

4.1.4 Description Job Engagement

Based on the work engagement variable, the lowest mean was found in indicator X2.1 with a mean value of 4.08. This value suggests that employee perceptions of the importance of personal involvement in work are still not as strong as those of other indicators in this variable. Overall, the work engagement variable falls into the good category, with an average of 4.17; however, there are still aspects that require improvement, particularly in fostering a sense of ownership and emotional attachment to work. Improvement in this aspect is important to encourage employees to be more deeply involved in their work activities.

4.1.5 Description Organizational Commitment

Based on the organizational commitment variable, the lowest mean was found in indicators X3.1 and X3.3, which both obtained a mean value of 4.14. This suggests that the sense of pride in being part of hotel management, as well as the balance between personal needs and the desire to continue working at the hotel, still need to be strengthened in comparison to other aspects of commitment. Overall, the organizational commitment variable falls into the good category, with an average mean of 4.17; however, strengthening employee identification with the organization and fostering the intrinsic desire to remain are still areas that require further attention.

Improvement efforts can be focused on creating a work environment that builds pride and emotional attachment to the organization.

4.1.6 Employee Performance Description

Based on employee performance variables, the lowest mean was found in the indicator of the ability to complete work according to targets, with a value of 4.07, which indicates that although employees generally meet targets, there is still room for improvement in the effectiveness of task completion. In addition, several other indicators, such as finding new, more effective ways (4.08) and understanding SOPs well (4.10), also had relatively low mean values, indicating the need for improvements in work innovation and understanding of operational procedures. Overall, employee performance variables showed promising results, with an average of 4.12. However, increasing focus on improving effectiveness, innovation, and understanding of work procedures would help drive more optimal performance in the work environment of star-rated hotels in Semarang City.

4.2 Discussion

The results of this study indicate that organizational culture has a significant impact on increasing employee job satisfaction. A strong and positive organizational culture fosters a work environment that promotes shared values, including open communication, collaboration, and appreciation for individual contributions. According to Schein & Schein (2017), organizational culture consists of basic assumptions, values, and norms that shape employee behavior and attitudes. When organizational culture aligns with employee needs and expectations, it fosters a sense of belonging and emotional attachment, which in turn increases job satisfaction (Robbins & Judge, 2019).

The results of this study align with those of Platania et al. (2022), who stated that organizational culture has a significant influence on job satisfaction because it reflects the values, norms, and practices that shape the work environment and employee experiences. An organizational culture that values fairness, inclusion, and support tends to create a positive work environment, thereby increasing employee loyalty and satisfaction. When organizational values align with employees' personal values, the psychological connection between the individual and the workplace is strengthened, resulting in higher motivation and engagement.

The results of this study are also in line with those of Reidhead (2020), who found that organizational

culture has a significant influence on employee job satisfaction. Other research also clearly demonstrates that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on employee job satisfaction levels, as indicated in the research results. Ahamed, & Mahmood (2015); Pawirosumarto et al. (2017); Fidyah & Setiawati (2020); And Ariani (2023).

The research results in the hotel industry that confirm the results of this research are as per: the research results conducted by Marwaha et al. (2024); Dawson et al. (2023); And Dirisu et al. (2018) that organizational culture was found to be an important element that greatly influences job satisfaction and employee performance, especially those working in the hospitality industry.

Developing a positive organizational culture is a strategic step that management must prioritize to increase employee job satisfaction. A culture that instills values of togetherness, mutual respect, and open communication can create a conducive and enjoyable work environment. In practice, managers must actively foster this culture by modeling consistent behavior, providing opportunities for employees to express their ideas and concerns, and ensuring that each individual feels valued and cared for. A strong and healthy culture can motivate employees to contribute optimally and increase loyalty to the organization.

Furthermore, integrating organizational culture into human resource policies and practices is crucial to supporting job satisfaction. Employee training and development should focus not only on improving technical skills but also on instilling the desired organizational cultural values. A fair and transparent reward and recognition system should also be developed to provide tangible appreciation for employee contributions. This way, employees feel cared for and motivated, which in turn improves their job satisfaction and overall performance.

Management should also regularly evaluate organizational culture to ensure it remains relevant and supports employee needs and organizational goals. Involving employees in the evaluation process through surveys, focus groups, or other communication forums can provide valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the existing culture. This participatory approach not only strengthens employee ownership of the organization but also allows management to make timely adjustments to the culture strategy. Through ongoing and responsive management of organizational culture, organizations can continually enhance employee job satisfaction and achieve superior performance.

“Mapping of Organizational Culture, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment in the Star-Rated Hotel Industry in Semarang City”

This study presents a novel approach by comprehensively integrating organizational culture variables into the context of their influence on job satisfaction. This aspect has not been extensively studied in this research area. While many previous studies have discussed organizational culture in general, this study examines explicitly how various dimensions of organizational culture, such as communication, shared values, and work norms, directly influence employee job satisfaction. This approach provides a more detailed and contextualized understanding of the mechanisms by which organizational culture influences specific work environments.

Furthermore, this study strengthens the existing literature by utilizing up-to-date empirical data that depict real-world conditions at the research site, allowing for a more valid and relevant analysis of the impact of organizational culture. Another novelty lies in the use of an analytical method that simultaneously reveals the causal relationships and significance levels of organizational culture's influence on job satisfaction, providing a more comprehensive picture compared to previous studies that tended to focus on a single dimension.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of descriptive analysis, this study concludes that organizational culture, work engagement, and organizational commitment in star-rated hotels in Semarang City are generally well-established and perceived positively by employees. Organizational culture is reflected through relatively strong work values, although aspects of decentralized decision-making, employee initiative, and job security still require strengthening. Employee work engagement is also in the good category, but strengthening the sense of ownership and emotional attachment to work is an aspect that requires management attention.

Organizational commitment shows a positive level, particularly in terms of employee loyalty and desire to remain a member of the organization. However, pride and intrinsic attachment to the organization could still be improved. Meanwhile, employee performance at star-rated hotels in Semarang City is generally considered good. However, there is still room for improvement in terms of target achievement, work innovation, and understanding of standard operating procedures.

Overall, the findings of this study emphasize the importance of sustainable management of internal organizational factors as a foundation for improving employee performance. Strengthening a supportive organizational culture, increasing work engagement, and

fostering more profound organizational commitment are expected to support improvements in service quality and the competitiveness of star-rated hotels in Semarang, amid an increasingly competitive hospitality industry.

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“Mapping of Organizational Culture, Job Involvement, and Organizational Commitment in the Star-Rated Hotel Industry in Semarang City”

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